

We used the consent form version available at the time of the study, in accordance with the data protection policy of the University of Paderborn, which can be accessed at the following URL: <https://www.uni-paderborn.de/en/university/data-protection>

We share the version we used in our study, an older version, below, omitting our own contact information.

We omit Section 1 and contact information here; Section 2 and the following read as follows:

2. Data category/s, purpose/s and legal basis/s of the processing of your personal data

The following mentioned audio and video recordings and other personal data are processed for the following purposes:

For the purpose of the audio interview: Gender, profession/position (professional experience in security and privacy), seniority, place of work (continent), interview questions on the topic "Security and Privacy Advice for UPI Users in India"

The initial consent to participate in the interview study is recorded and stored using LimeSurvey (local instance at Paderborn University).

If you are willing to participate in the interview study, an appointment for the audio interview will be arranged by email (university account of Paderborn University).

The audio interviews are conducted with Zoom (license of the University of Paderborn), recorded, and stored locally.

The saved file of the audio interview is given a pseudonymized identifier.

The audio interviews are sent to the transcription service provider Zoom (license of the University of Paderborn), where they are transcribed and de-identified. The de-identified transcripts are cross-checked by the working group.

The de-identified transcripts are evaluated using qualitative analysis software such as MAXQDA.

Note:

Subsequent publications of the evaluation results will only be made with de-identified data.

- Audio and video recordings of the interviews are saved and transcribed. All personal data is removed from the transcripts or made unrecognizable. Afterwards, the transcripts are used for research purposes. After checking transcripts for correctness, audio and video recordings will be discarded. Audio and video recordings will never be made public, and only used to create and check transcripts for correctness.
- If requested, email addresses will be retained, if applicable, to inform the participant of the results of the study.

The legal basis for this processing of your personal data is your consent pursuant to Art. 6 para. 1 subpara. 1 lit. a) DS-GVO (if applicable, Art. 88 DS-GVO in conjunction with § 18 para. 1 DSG NRW) (preparation of the recording(s)) and according to Art. 6 para. 1 UAbs. 1 lit. a) DS-GVO (if applicable Art. 88 DS-GVO in conjunction with § 18 para. 1 DSG NRW) or § 22 KUG (use of the recording(s)).

The processing of the above-mentioned further personal data is also based on Art. 6 para. 1 UAbs. 1 lit. a) DS-GVO (if applicable Art. 88 DS-GVO in conjunction with § 18 para. 1 DSG NRW).

3. Recipients of your personal data

The recording(s) made will be passed on as described below:

Zoom (license of the University of Paderborn), If (technical) service providers are given access to personal data, this is done on the basis of a contract in accordance with Art. 28 GDPR. For data processing that takes place with other controllers, this is done, if necessary, on the basis of an agreement in accordance with Art. 26 GDPR. In individual cases, personal data may be disclosed on the basis of legal permission.

4. Data transfer of your personal data outside the EU

As a matter of principle, no personal data is transferred to countries outside the European Economic Area and associated countries (no "third country transfer").

5. Duration of the storage of your personal data

The recordings of your interview will be stored subject to the revocation of your consent for 6 months-for a specific purpose. Beyond that, retention periods may apply.

6. Data subject rights

As a data subject, you may at any time exercise the rights granted to you by the GDPR; these are:

- the right to information as to whether and which of your data is being processed in accordance with Art. 15 DS-GVO; § 12 DSG NRW;
- the right to request the correction or completion of data concerning you in accordance with Art. 16 DS-GVO;
- the right to have the data concerning you deleted in accordance with Art. 17 DS-GVO; § 10 DSG NRW
- the right to restrict the processing of data concerning you in accordance with Art. 18 DS-GVO;
- the right to data transfer of the data concerning you in accordance with Art. 20 DS-GVO.

7. Revocability of your consent

Your consent to the processing of your photo, video and/or audio recordings described above can be revoked in whole or in part at any time without giving reasons with effect for the future. The legality of the data processing carried out on the basis of the consent until the revocation is not affected by this (Art. 7 para. 3 DS-GVO). If you revoke your consent, your personal data may no longer be processed unless there is also another legal basis for the processing (Art. 17 (1) (b) DS-GVO). To exercise the right of withdrawal, please contact the above-mentioned contact.

8. Right to complain

In addition to the aforementioned rights, you have the right to file a complaint with the supervisory authority under data protection law (Art. 77 DS-GVO) if you believe that the processing of personal data concerning you violates the requirements of data protection law; for example, with the State Commissioner for Data Protection and Freedom of Information of North Rhine-Westphalia responsible for the University of Paderborn.

Declaration of consent for the production and/or use of photo, video and/or audio recordings and, if applicable, other personal data within the scope of "Vulnerability disclosure in security research".

For:

[first and last name]

E-mail address

The University of Paderborn intends to make and/or use the photo, video and/or audio recordings named below for the purposes named below. In order to make and/or use the recordings, the University of

Paderborn requires your consent to make and/or use the recordings; the subject of this declaration of consent is/are the following recording(s) and, if applicable, further personal data:

- Participation in the LimeSurvey questionnaire
- Contact to arrange an appointment for the audio interview, including conducting, recording, storage and transcription by Zoom
- Evaluation of the data (LimeSurvey questionnaire and audio interview) in the context of the question of the interview study "Vulnerability disclosure in security research" with the use of MAXQDA

I agree to be recorded as described above and/or to have the recordings used by us as described above.

The consent is voluntary. No consequences arise from a refusal.

The consent can be revoked in whole or in part at any time with effect for the future without giving reasons. The revocation shall not affect the lawfulness of the processing carried out until then on the basis of the consent. In the event of revocation, the relevant personal data may no longer be processed for the above-mentioned purposes in the future. To exercise the right of revocation, please contact the above-mentioned contact.

I have received and taken note of the information sheet on the processing of my personal data in accordance with Art. 13 DS-GVO in the context of the production and/or use of photo, video and/or audio recordings.

[Place, date, signature /en]

In the case of a minor, the signature of the legal guardian is also required.